

A TECHNOLOGICAL APPROACH TO ADDRESS DEFICIENCIES IN UID (AADHAAR)

Rishabh Garg

Department of Electrical & Electronics Engineering,
Birla Institute of Technology & Science, K.K. Birla Goa Campus, Sancoale, Goa - 403726, India
rishabhgargdps@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In order to provide an official identity to every citizen of India, the Department of Information Technology, had proposed an idea of biometric enabled unique identification number (UID). The system preserves the personally identifiable information (PII) of millions of users on a centralized government database, supported by some legacy software, with numerous SPOF (single points of failures). Such a centralized system, containing PII, acts like a honey pot to hackers.

In a country where 2/3rd of the vulnerable citizens, do not have a bank account, but own a smartphone, echoes the possibility of a mobile based digital identity solution. The blockchain technology, by virtue of its key features like decentralization, persistency, anonymity and auditability, emerges as the most promising one amongst all.

KEYWORDS

Asynchronous Byzantine Fault Tolerance, Authentication, Blockchain, Channel, Cryptography, DApps, Data Portability, Decentralized Public Key Infrastructure (DPKI), DID, Ethereum, Hash function, Hashgraph, IAM framework, Identity Management System (IMS), Private Key, Public Key, Proof of Work algorithm, Revocation, SSI, Validation, Zero Knowledge Proof.

1. INTRODUCTION

India is a Nation that has more than three dozen of IDs, certificates and licenses. At each level, one has to procure a series of documents, some of which require renewal, periodically [1], [2]. An average Indian has to carry at least 3-5 different documents and existing IDs, and they serve different and limited purpose only. As citizens are issued different identity proofs for different purposes, there is a lack of resemblance in citizen's profile among different data repositories, thus causing inconsistency and recurrence [3].

The need of a single National ID for a large country, like India, becomes more crucial than for the many other countries that have already adopted such a system or intend to do so. Provision of multiple services to a large population by government and private organizations is a gigantic task and is strewn with many hurdles. A digital National ID would help in improved banking, investment services, health facilities and different public distribution schemes offered by the government [4]. A Digital ID will reinforce national and social security for citizens, and serve as an instrument for citizens to access multiple government and private services [5].

The quest for a single ID started in the year 1993 with the inception of Electors Photo Identity Card (popularly known as voter ID or EPIC), in the pretext to bring transparency in electoral process and to enable voter's identification on Election Day. Until now, more than 450 million voters hold election identity cards across the country. Though, it serves as an identity tool and address proof to open a bank account; fetch a new gas connection; make an online reservation

for travel; or to book an accommodation, yet it could not become an all-purpose national ID owing to limited operations.

The idea of a Universal Identity was proposed by the Department of Information Technology, Government of India, in 2006. With a primary objective to provide a biometrics enabled identity number to every resident of India, a Unique Identification Authority of India (UIDAI) was established under the aegis of Planning Commission in June 2009. The flagship project of UIDAI, known as Aadhaar, became the world's largest National Identity Project, which collected biometric and demographic data of residents and stored them in a centralized electronic repository. Initially, it seemed as an opportunity to create a super identity - one that is more portable, traceable, and has little or no chance of being misused or getting leaked.

Prior to the enactment of the Aadhaar Act, there were no regulations in India, for the process of collecting, handling, storage, access, retrieval, disclosure and destruction of sensitive personal information, by any service providers [6]. Under the Aadhaar Act 2016, UIDAI is held responsible for Aadhaar enrolment and authentication, including operation and management of all stages of Aadhaar life-cycle, simultaneously developing the policy, procedure and implementation system, for issue of Aadhaar numbers to individuals. It is also accountable for security of information, along with maintenance of authentication records of individuals.

2. UID AS A CENTRALIZED IDENTITY

In India, a unique ID system, called Aadhaar, has been prevalent for last twelve years. It carries a 12-digit individual identification number, issued by UIDAI, on behalf of the Government of India. The Government perceives Aadhaar card as a tool for better governance, as each Aadhaar number is unique to an individual and remains valid unto death. It aimed to:

- ✓ achieve social inclusion with more efficient public and private service delivery;
- ✓ reduce the large number of fake and duplicate identities; and
- ✓ pave the way for direct benefit transfers.

Aadhaar was conceptualized to provide an identity to those residents who did not have any individual identity or who had multiple identities. The basic idea was to create a super identity, which is traceable and less susceptible of being misused. The government came up with an idea of creating a single biometric identification system that could be monitored by UIDAI, and may allow Indian residents to access and utilize public services.

2.1 UID: Salient Features

Some of the salient features of UID project as mentioned in the UIDAI draft [7] are enumerated here under:

- The UID, a random generated number, without any coding intelligence, will function, to minimize chances of fraudulence. However, UIDAI will prove identity only and will not indicate citizenship status.
- The enrolment process for UID number will be voluntary
- The UIDAI will only issue a number to the individual that can be printed on a card like PAN card or voter's ID, which will remain the same unto death.
- The UIDAI will determine KYR (know your resident) standards, for the UID enrolment process, to prevent fraudulent practices.
- The UIDAI will form a Central Identity Data Repository (CIDR) to serve as a managed service provider and will ensure core services
- In order to expedite the enrolment process, the UIDAI planned to partner with the existing government and non-government agencies, across the Country, and took leverage of their infrastructure, for the entire process.

2.2 UID: Standards

The data, used in UID, encompasses Biometrics Data and Demographics Data [8]. Biometric system has been adopted on the basis of three different biometric data, all ten finger prints; iris scan; and face recognition of every individual [9]. Multimodal system allows the integration of two or more types of biometric recognition and verification, in order to meet stringent performance requirements.

The demographic details for Aadhaar collected by UIDAI comprise, Personal Details, Address Details, Parents Details, Introducer Details and Contact Details. In order to verify the information submitted by residents, three distinct methods of verification were employed - support documents, personal introducer and NPR (National Population Register) [10].

2.3 UIDAI: Ecosystem

- The enrolment architecture consists of network of Registrars and Enrolment Agencies. Registrar is a unit, authorized by UIDAI, for the purpose of enrolling individuals, which in turn, appoints the Enrolment Agencies that are responsible for collecting biometric and demographic information during the enrolment process. The latter completes its task by involving certified Operators/ Supervisors.
- Unique Identification Project includes unique entities like UIDAI, Enrolment Station and a Central Identities Data Repository (CIDR), which co-exist and function in close harmony. The UIDAI has also appointed a number of Authentication Service Agencies (ASAs) and Authentication User Agencies (AUAs) from various Government and non-Government organizations.

A biometric system adopted by UIDAI is mainly a pattern recognition system that obtains biometric data from an individual, then extracts a feature set from the acquired data, and finally, compares this feature set against the standard template set in the database. As a result, a random number, irrespective of any classification, is generated as a unique identity of an individual. In response to identification queries, the UIDAI authenticates as a 'Yes' or 'No' [11].

To establish an individual identity, the system hunts, all the templates of the users in the database, to find a good match. Therefore, the system conducts a one-to-several comparison. Identification is a critical component in negative recognition applications, where the system establishes whether the person is, who he denies to be. Negative recognition helps to prevent a person from using multiple identities.

In the verification mode, an individual's identity is validated by equating his biometric template stored in the database with that of the captured biometric data. In such a case, a person, who needs to be recognized, claims an identity, through a personal identification number (PIN), a user name, or an IC enabled card, and the system conducts one-to-one comparison to ascertain the validity of claim. Identity verification, commonly termed as positive recognition, is normally used to prevent more than one person from using the same identity.

Since the authentication service is provided in real-time, the UIDAI has established two data centres, one where authentication is done and the other, where online services such as e-KYC are deployed in active-active mode, to ensure high availability. The financial institutions and payment network operators have embedded Aadhaar authentication into their micro-ATMs, to permit branch-less banking all over the country in a real-time, accessible and interoperable manner.

2.4 UID: Benefits

In a heterogeneous and diverse country, like India, implementation of UID was indeed a challenge, at socio-economic, political and technological front. Aadhaar, with a portable ID, has empowered the excluded and deprived sections of the society. JAM (Jan Dhan-Aadhaar-Mobile) trinity served as a bridge to connect public funds, mobile numbers and Aadhaar cards, to

transfer subsidies and eliminate intermediaries to stop leakages. This enabled Banking correspondents to approach the rural sector, facilitating banking transactions.

The state governments have been advised to implement Aadhaar based Direct Benefit Transfers (DBT) to individual beneficiaries for all Central government funded schemes. Withdrawal of EPF, monthly pension and income tax PAN after linking with Aadhaar, are some of the benefits, to state. It also served as a tool for the financial inclusion and socio-economic development of the Country.

One of the major breakthroughs of Aadhaar was evident, in the procurement process of Passport. It has significantly slashed down the time-consuming police verification process and paved the way for release of Passport within 10 days. Probably, that could be the reason, why Aadhaar Card has emerged as a mandatory document for obtaining Passport.

2.5 UID: Pitfalls

Despite an expenditure of 12,873.93 Cr INR, the government has not been able to achieve 100% targets over a period of ten years. This implies that ≥ 10 Cr marginalized residents, who are in dire need of access to limited benefits provided by the State, are still living dispossessed [12].

Fig - 1: Saturation Status (in percentage) of Aadhaar as on April 2021.

The UID project was a critical initiative for India and in all possibilities, the government had to be quite sure that the project would not meet the same fate as it had, in similar other large scale exercises, like introduction of EPIC in the country. Unfortunately, the over-enthusiastic political and administrative fraternity never ventured into the pros and cons, which a common man manage to see, probably as a hindsight effect [13].

Aadhaar number, which was imagined by the government, as a general proof of identity and proof of address could not hold ground because various existing forms of identity still continue and the requirement of furnishing other documents for proof of address, even after the issue of Aadhaar number, make its existence, meaningless. Aadhaar cannot be considered neutral as the documentary proofs collected for Aadhaar reveal sensitive information [14].

Aadhaar inherently carries a lot of personal and private information like biometrics, fingerprints; it eventually defies the data privacy. Our Country does not have any data protection law, at the moment and the right to privacy does not find any explicit clause in the Constitution except incidentally under Articles 19(1)(a) and Article 21. Besides Constitution, the only legal instrument to protect privacy, is the Information Technology Act, 2000; Section 43 A [15].

Over the last decade, there have been multiple instances of Aadhaar data leaking online, through government websites. Recently, an RTI query coaxed UIDAI to admit that about 210 government websites unveiled the Aadhaar details on internet. Centre for Internet and Society (CIS) has also drawn attention to about 130 million Aadhaar numbers with details, available on

internet [16]. An IIT graduate was arrested for building an app called Aadhaar e-KYC, by hacking into the servers related to an e-Hospital system, created under the Digital India initiative. UIDAI has regularly shut down fraudulent websites and mobile apps that claim to render Aadhaar services to users. After becoming become conscious of the fact that Aadhaar portal could be accessed without authorization, UIDAI blocked around 5,000 officials from accessing the portal.

The saga does not end up here, as a journalist from *The Tribune*, unearthed another racket, which offered an access to the Aadhaar data, to individuals, using WhatsApp, to reach out to potential buyers. Apart from the typical hackers, breaching the security of Aadhaar database, some miscreants created fake Aadhaar cards, posing a problem for UIDAI. According to the Breach Level Index (BLI), computed by a digital security firm, almost one billion data records have been breached in India, since 2013.

Despite unprecedented surge of public information on social media, a large number of users are unaware of how technology services compromise their privacy [17]. Those, who are aware, want more regulations on the activities of governments and corporations providing such services [18], [19]. The legal framework within which governments and corporations operate often holds users themselves to be responsible for their privacy. Even in the United States, it is obligatory upon individuals to evaluate their choices and take responsibility for the decision they take [20].

In absence of a clear legislative and juridical understanding of information, in India, the UIDAI project needs to be thoroughly re-scrutinized and make immediate switch-over to some more dependable, decentralized and tamper-proof technology [21].

3. DIGITAL IDENTITY AS A SOLUTION

In order to have safe, secure and private digital identity, one technology that has risen to the top of the list, is the distributed ledger. The concept describes how cryptology and an open global ledger can be combined into a digital currency application [22].

A distributed ledger is a database that exists across several locations or among multiple participants. It could be a Blockchain, DAG, Hashgraph, Holochain or Tempo (Radix).

3.1 Blockchain

The blockchain is a type of DLT where transaction records are saved, in the ledger, as a chain of blocks. All the nodes maintain ledger, so the overall computational power gets distributed among them, which provides good outcome. Blockchain ensures:

- **Enhanced security:** Every single data is deeply encrypted (hashed) which allows a higher level of security. It renders hacking impossible.
- **Faster Disbursement:** Relatively faster than typical payment systems, although bigger networks may have slower transaction rates.
- **Consensus:** Supports a wide range of consensus algorithm that help the nodes to make the right decision.

Once a transaction takes place, the nodes on the network verifies it. After verification, the transaction gets a unique hash ID, along with the recent transaction hash ID, and gets stored in the ledger. Once it gets added to the ledger, no one can mutate or delete the transaction.

3.2 DAG (Directed Acyclic Graphs)

Every transaction is entered on the ledger in sequential order. However, to validate it, the transaction needs to validate two previous transactions to call itself valid. Here, a sequence of transaction is called a 'branch' and the longer does it go on, the more valid all the transaction become.

- **Virtually Infinite Scalability:** The more users use the network, the less time it takes for validation. That's how it can reach infinite level of scalability.

- Quantum-resistance: The use of one time signatures makes it Quantum-resistant.
- Parallel transactions: All transactions align in a parallel line after validation.

3.3 Hashgraph

Hashgraph employs a Gossip protocol to relay the information about a transaction. Once a transaction takes place, the adjoining nodes share that information with other ones, and after sometime all the nodes would know about the transaction. With the help of ‘Virtual Voting’ protocol, every node validates the transaction and then the transaction gets added to the ledger.

- There can be multiple transactions stored on the ledger on the same timestamp. All transactions are stored in a parallel structure. Here every record on the ledger is called an ‘Event’.
- Unique Data Structure: The ledger logs down every gossip sequence on the network in an orderly fashion.
- Random Gossip: Nodes randomly gossip about what they know with other nodes to spread the information until every node knows the information.

3.4 Holochain

In Holochain, every node on the network maintain their own ledger. Though the system does not prescribe any global validation protocol, yet the network maintains a set of rules called ‘DNA’ to verify every individual ledger.

- Holochain moves on from the data-centric structures to agent centric structures. Agent-centric nodes can validate individually without any forced consensus protocol.
- Energy efficient: The different nature of the ledger makes the system more energy efficient than its other equivalents.
- True DLT: Every node on the network maintains their own ledger, which creates a true distributed system.

3.5 Tempo (Radix)

- Logical clocks: The system relies on the sequence of the transactions, rather than timestamps, to reach consensus.
- Sharding: Every node on the network keeps a shard (smallest section of the global ledger) with a unique ID.
- Gossip protocol: Nodes broadcast all their information to synchronize their own shards.

Blockchain, owing to some of its unmatched properties, like decentralization, information transparency, openness and tamper-proof construction, seems to be a good match for identity management [23], [24], [25], [26].

Blockchain is regarded as a blue-print of New Era [27]. It can be employed in areas like education, health, science, transportation and logistics, other than currency and finance [28], [29], [30]. It encompasses a more advanced form of ‘smart contracts’ to set up a distributed organizational unit, which frames its own laws and works with a high degree of autonomy [31].

4. BLOCKCHAIN ARCHITECTURE

Blockchain is a sequence of blocks, which holds a complete list of transaction records like conventional public ledger [32]. With a previous block hash contained in the block header, a block has only one parent block. The first block of a blockchain is called genesis block, which has no parent block.

4.1 Block

A block comprises a block header and a block body as shown in Figure - 2. The block header contains block version, Merkle tree root hash, timestamp, nBits, nonce, and parent block hash. The block body comprises transaction Hash, transaction root, state hash, and state root.

Fig - 2: Block comprising block header and block body.

To check the integrity of the block, the hashes of all the components are used. To validate the block, additional conditions are checked.

4.2 Hash Function

Hash function, used in cryptography, depicts a mathematical algorithm that transforms information bit to a string of alphanumeric values. Hash functions have a high avalanche effect i.e., a small change in the input string results in a different output string. This makes it almost impossible to reverse engineering unless sophisticated ML algorithms are applied. Common hashing functions are SHA-3, SHA-256, Keccak. There are two types of hashing methods:

- i) Simple hashing is done by brute-force approach. It is suitable for documents / blocks with fixed amount of content / transactions. E.g. block header.
- ii) Merkle tree hash, where data is arranged as leaf nodes (binary tree) and hashing is done in sets of two leaves. E.g. composite block integrity; $O(n) = \log n$.

Fig - 3: Hash transforming information bit into a string of alphanumeric values.

4.3 Keys: Private and Public

In order to secure decentralized identities, private keys are known only to the owner, while public keys are disseminated widely. This pairing achieves two purposes. The first is

authentication, where the public key verifies that a holder of the paired private key has sent the message. The second is encryption, where only the paired private key holder can decrypt the message encrypted with the public key. This process is called cryptography.

4.4 Decentralized Identifiers

Fig - 4: DID (Decentralized Identifiers)

A decentralized identifier (DID) or a pseudo-anonymous identifier is secured by a private key. Only the private key owner can control his identity. One person can have many DIDs, which limits the extent to which they can be tracked across the multiple activities in their life.

4.5 Tokens

The merger of blockchain with tokens is a vital combination of Blockchain 3.0. Token is an attestation of digital rights, and therefore blockchain tokens are widely recognized with due credit to Ethereum and its ERC20 standard. Based on this parameter, anyone can issue a custom token on Ethereum and this token can indicate any right or value. Tokens can act as a type of validation of any right, including personal identity, educational diplomas, currency, receipts, keys, rebate points, vouchers, stocks, and bonds. It can be stated that tokens are its front-end economic face while blockchain is the middle and back-end technology of the new age identity.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Thus, utilizing blockchain technology, one can introduce a digital identity ecosystem that combines authentication capabilities and enhanced individual privacy protection, to generate a frictionless experience of identity [33]. By using blockchain technology, both citizens and organizations can be assured about the security and protection of data. Distributed ledger technologies (DLT), blockchain being the most well-known example here, ensure that information is never held at single repository; rather it's securely managed in decentralized databases. The consumers can also share their information with the service provider without risk of it being exposed publicly.

Another strong advantage of digital identity is its capability to streamline administrative processes, thereby enhancing the productivity of departments or services. The digital identity ecosystem can work seamlessly around the World, to connect different service providers, across multiple countries through use of DLT. Organizations can minimize the time spent on tedious tasks that includes customer service calls or entering data from the application forms submitted by the citizens.

In addition to organizations, a digital identity platform would help customers by allowing them to save time when accessing or providing their personal data and records. Instead of physical presence, to produce a physical form of ID, consumers could be provided with a digital ID through a personal device, like their Smartphone [34], that can be shared with services conveniently and securely through a DLT.

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